

Insect resistance

Reaction of rice cultivars to pink stem borer (PSB)

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In 1981 kharif we screened 84 rices for reaction to PSB *Sesamia inferens* in the field at Hawalbagh, Almora, where the pest is endemic. Thirty-day-old seedlings were transplanted, 2 plants/hill at 20- × 10-cm spacing in 2-row plots 2.5 m long.

Test varieties selected were stem borer-resistant and tolerant entries from various national and international nurs-

eries that were screened at Hawalbagh in 1980. VL 8 and China 1039 were the resistant and susceptible checks.

Pest incidence was heavy from Sep-Oct to panicle bearing. Whiteheads caused by stem tunnelling were counted at peak incidence on 10 hills of each variety, 75-80 d after transplanting. Cultivars were scored as resistant (0-5% infestation), moderately resistant (5.1-10%), susceptible (10.1-25%), and highly susceptible (above 25%).

Eight cultivars were resistant and 11 were moderately resistant. The rest were susceptible or highly susceptible (see table). □

Varietal resistance to PSB, Hawalbagh, India.

Reaction	Cultivars
Resistant (0-5%)	HPU803, HPU2199, IR9129-192-24-3, IR9758-150-3, IR19774-34-2-1, KAU 2110, VRS163-2-3, VRS291-3-1, VL8 (resistant check)
Moderately resistant (5.1-10%)	ARC11981, Fuzi 102, IR2053-521-1-1, IR7167-33-2-5, IR9129-263-3-3-2-3, IR9782-111-2-1, IRAT102, K228-8-3, K427, VRS245-2-1, VRS598-3-1

Genetics of resistance to whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) in two rices

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WBPH *Sogatella furcifera* Horvath causes serious damage in Madhya Pradesh, Uttar Pradesh, and Punjab. The insect lives with brown planthopper (BPH) at the base of rice plants and causes hopperburn.

We studied the genetics of resistance to WBPH in two resistant varieties: Balamawee and ARC10464. The two were crossed with susceptible TN1. Balamawee and ARC10464 also were crossed to learn the allelic relationship of the resistance

genes. The F₁ and F₂ populations were evaluated for WBPH reaction by bulk screening (see table)

Resistance in each of Balamawee and ARC10464 is governed by a single recessive gene. In both the crosses with TN1, the F₁ plants were susceptible and

the F₂ plants segregated as 3 susceptible: 1 resistant. In the cross Balamawee/ARC10464, the F₁ plants were susceptible and the F₂ segregated as 9 susceptible: 7 resistant, indicating that the recessive genes for resistance in both varieties are nonallelic. □

Reaction^a of F₁ and F₂ populations to WBPH, Pantnagar, India.

Cross	F ₁ reaction	Total (no.)	F ₂ reaction			X ²	P value
			R (no.)	S (no.)	Assumed genetic ratio		
TN1/Balamawee	S	137	39	98	1:3	0.88	0.50-0.30
TN1/ARC10464	S	136	40	96	1:3	1.41	0.30-0.20
Balamawee/ARC10464	S	189	77	112	7:9	0.56	0.50-0.30

^aS = susceptible, R = resistant.

Promising gall midge (GM) resistant rices with short to medium duration

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In the northern Telangana region of Andhra Pradesh, uncertain monsoon

conditions delay rice planting and crops suffer severe GM infestation. GM damage is particularly serious in Sep and Oct when there are high rainfall and humidity and many cloudy days.

We sought to develop 110- to 140-d varieties with GM resistance. Following are some popular GM-resistant varieties developed at ARS.

Surekha (IR8/Siam 29) is 80 cm tall with dark green foliage and erect leaves. It has 130- to 135-d duration and is suitable only for the monsoon season. It is lodging resistant, fertilizer responsive, and can be planted in late Jul. If planted late, 10- × 10-cm spacing is recommended. Each panicle has about 170 long, slender, translucent grains. Seed

dormancy is 10-15 d at harvest. It yields 5.5 to 6.0 t/ha.

WGL 22245 (IR579/W12708) is 80 cm tall with compact panicles. Leaves have a purple margin. It is photoperiod-insensitive with 125-d duration in monsoon and 135 d in winter. Grains are translucent. It has stem borer (SB) and

bacterial blight resistance, and yields 6.0 to 7.5 t/ha. It is recommended for release as Pothana.

WGL 26889 (IR22/12708) is a 145-d variety suitable for the monsoon season. It is SB-resistant with fine grains, and yields an average 6.0 t/ha. It is being tested in minikit trials.

WGL 20506 (Tella Hamsa/W12708) has 105-d duration and is especially suited for sowing in late monsoon, as late as mid-Aug. Grains are long and slender with a light brown husk. Yield averages 4.5 to 5.0 t/ha. □

Reaction of yellow stem borer (YSB) resistant accessions to other rice pests

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In the greenhouse we tested six accessions with resistance and moderate resistance to YSB for resistance to brown planthopper (BPH), whitebacked planthopper (WBPH), green leafhopper (GLH), leafhopper (LF), white leafhopper (WLH), and rice tungro virus (RTV).

W1263 was resistant to LF, BPH, WBPH, and GLH and moderately resistant to RTV (see table). Co 18 and

Reaction of YSB resistant accessions to major rice pests and RTV, Coimbatore, India.

Accession	Mean resistance rating ^a						
	YSB	GLH	WLH	BPH	WBPH	LF	RTV ^b
W1263	1.0 a	4.0 a	6.3 bc	3.6 a	4.3 a	1.8 a	5.0 a
Co 18	4.0 bc	6.0 ab	3.6 a	3.6 a	3.6 a	6.2 bc	7.6 c
IR13641-4	4.0 bc	7.0 bc	6.3 bc	7.6 cd	5.0 ab	6.6 c	7.0 bc
IR13639-39	4.0 bc	5.6 ab	5.6 b	5.6 b	5.0 ab	5.4 b	5.0 a
Sornavazhai	6.5 c	7.0 bc	7.6 cd	3.0 a	4.3 a	9.0 d	7.0 bc
Jaya (susceptible)	9.0 d	6.5 abc	5.0 ab	7.0 bc	6.3 ab	9.0 d	9.0 d
TN1	—	9.0 c	9.0 d	9.0 d	7.6 b	—	—

^aBy the 1980 Standard Evaluation System for Rice. In a column, means followed by the same letter are not statistically different. ^bRating scale based on field evaluation.

IR13639-39 were moderately resistant to BPH, WBPH, and WLH. IR13641-4 was moderately resistant to WBPH and

moderately susceptible to other pests. Sornavazhai was resistant to BPH and WBPH. □

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Adverse soils tolerance

Tolerance for iron deficiency in rice

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Fe deficiency is a major constraint to increasing the area planted to high yielding varieties in the calcareous soils of north Bihar. Major calcareous areas are in Gopalganj, Saran, Siwan, Vaishali, Muzaffarpur, Samastipur, Begusarai, East Champaran, and parts of West Champaran and Darbhanga.

Soils have pH 7.7 to 9.8, electrical conductivity 0.1 to 4.2 dS/m, 0.1 to 1.0% organic carbon, 4 to 49% available CaCO₃, and low available P. Nurseries are dry-seeded and seedling leaves whiten in the nursery beds. Fe deficiency

symptoms are yellowing of young leaves and interveinal chlorosis which becomes whitish yellow, then ivory.

Varieties differ in susceptibility to Fe deficiency. We screened lines for Fe deficiency in the field at Pusa beginning in 1981 wet season. The first trial was non-replicated. In the next, tolerant lines were evaluated in three replications. Symptoms

were visible 15 to 20 d after seeding. IET7972 and IET7973 were tolerant of Fe deficiency. Br 34, Br 8, and TCA84 were moderately tolerant (Table 1). Most of the released varieties were susceptible to highly susceptible. Tolerant and moderately tolerant entries were photoperiod sensitive and are pureline selections from land races.

Table 1. Varietal reaction of certain elite lines to Fe deficiency, Samastipur, India.

Tolerance score	Plant infection (%)	Line
1	up to 1	IET7972 (TCA148-3), IET7973 (TCA62-31-1)
3	1 – 5	Br34, Br8, TCA84
5	5 – 25	UPR238-42-2-3, IET5882, UPR79-17, T141, NP49, IET6263
7	25 – 50	Rasi (IET1444, Pankaj, Janaki (IET9971), IET7970, KMP40, IET5883
9	50 – 100	Pusa 33, Pusa 2-21, Ratna, Rajendra Dhan 201, Sita, Jaya, Mahsuri, Saket 4, Radha (IET6261), UPR79-14, IR4568-86-1-2-3, RP1045-403-1, IR1157-52, UPR254-81-1-TCA, Br9, Katarni